

MAN IS THE CREATOR OF HISTORY AND THE GREATEST SOCIAL VALUE. (his biosocial essence)

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Annotation: In this article, we discuss the theories about the origin of man, the separation of man from the animal world, and the theories that consciousness and thinking are the supreme criteria for distinguishing man. Also, the doctrines of biosocial activity as a human value are briefly explained.

Key words: consciousness, thinking, language, genetic characteristics, moral, family, norms, I. Kant, Beruni, Farobi, Pratagoras, Democritus.

Introduction.

Man is a fundamental philosophical category that forms the basis of any doctrine. In order to give a clear definition of the human concept, it is necessary to determine the most important features that distinguish it from other biological beings in the world. It is necessary to emphasize that, first of all, a person is distinguished from other creatures by the presence of his memory, thinking, language, that is, by the presence of consciousness. In particular, language performs the function of succession, connection between his ancestors and descendants. In a word, it acts as a communicative link between ancestors and descendants. All genetic characteristics, moral norms, and programs that control the human race are transmitted from ancestors to generations through this language. One of the characteristics that characterizes the fundamental difference of man from other living creatures is the ability to regulate his practical activities, that is, he can respond to everything he does at the level of consciousness. This situation means that culture is the most important feature that determines the humanity of a person.

Also, the ability of a person to produce the material and spiritual wealth necessary for his life is one of these characteristics. Work plays a major role in human life. Thanks to work, a person changes the natural environment in which he lives, creates material and spiritual wealth, and changes himself. Pure physiological functions of the human body, the development of hands and feet, thumbs and fingers, ankles, tendons, bones and muscles are also directly related to work. The reason is that a person came to this appearance as a result of adapting to nature and conditions through work. In addition, work is the main condition for not only physical, but also spiritual and cultural development of a person. At this point, it should be said that language is one of the reasons for the unity of a person in a community, because the exchange of communication caused the separation of a person from an animal. Due to work, man affects nature. For this purpose, he makes work tools and continuously improves these tools.

Discussion.

Moral norms of family relations are one of the most important characteristics of a person, different from an animal.

A person is formed as a moral being, the process of turning a biological being into a social being has taken place. With the help of simple moral norms, primitive communities forced their members to follow the rules and disciplines acceptable to all. The same situation indicates that a person is completely separated from an animal. In turn, this event was a great victory of the social state over the biological state. It was a great Neolithic revolution when man learned to work, to make tools, and to observe moral norms. Due to this neolithic revolution, man gradually became socialized. The first ancestor of man began to move from activity based on hunting and gathering to a lifestyle based on productivity and creativity (farming, animal husbandry, farming, etc.). The same situation indicates that a person is being formed as a socio-historical being and is being embodied.

Today, philosophers say that a person is a combination of three great powers - body, mind and spirit. The biological state of a person means the electro-chemical changes that occur in his body, the symptoms that represent his age, race and gender.

When thinking about a person's mental state, his feelings, moods, experiences, and temperament are understood.

Human spirituality is a set of qualities, feelings, abilities, skills formed as a result of objective conditions and subjective factors existing in society.

The human problem has always been at the center of philosophical teachings. The first philosophical teachings about man and his essence were developed in Ancient India and later in China.

Philosophical analysis of human problems rose to great heights in Ancient Greece. According to the Greek philosophers, it is a less perfect view of the Greek Universe, consisting of body, soul and spirit representing all its elements. Within the universe, man exists side by side with gods, all living beings - plants and animals.

The special placement of the human problem in the center of philosophical teachings is fully expressed in the opinion of Protogoras that "Man is the measurer of all things".

For Democritus, man is a part of nature, therefore he is also made of atoms. According to Democritus, the purpose of life is spiritual happiness.

The rational approach to this issue was strong in religious and philosophical teachings in the regions where Islam spread in the East.

Representatives of Islamic philosophy dealt with all the main aspects of the human problem. In particular, they were interested in issues such as the origin of man, his place in the world, the possibilities of mastering reality, the ideal of a person who has chosen the path of virtue, etc. As a result of the analysis of these issues, Al-Faroabi came to the conclusion that the difference between man and all creatures is in his intelligence, while Ibn Sina interprets intelligence as the ability to think about general views and specific things.

Literature review.

Beruni's thoughts on this problem are also important. He acknowledged that man was created by God, and at the same time pointed out that his whole life and physical structure are also related to geographical factors; "The human body, color, true appearance, and natural features depend not only on the origin, but also on the soil, water, air, and place of residence." [1:1986,67-b].

The analysis of the human problem differs in quality from the teachings existing in the past eras, according to the place it occupies in all stages of the philosophy of the New Age, and its importance. In the thinking of the renaissance era, which was not in any of the teachings of the past, the human condition was revealed as a unique individuality, it was shown that humanity is made up of unique people. From this, it was concluded that human nature is not the same as in living nature, and at the same time there are important points where the interests of man and humanity are in common.

Philosophical analyzes of individualism, egoism (selfishness), self-interest began to be seen in the philosophy of this period, firstly, the issue of man, his special conditions and limitlessness of possibilities.

For the German classical founder I. Kant, "Man is the most basic creature in the world", on the one hand, he belongs to nature, on the other hand, he is morally free, and thirdly, he always deals with values[2:2006,40-b].

In the first of these qualities, a person is faced with necessity, and in the second, he has spiritual freedom.

Man is a biosocial creature, he has a social essence as well as a biological essence. The study of this issue has been relevant since the earliest history of man. After all, at the same time, a person creates problems for living nature, and directly, in principle, puts the issues of worldview on the agenda. This can be understood from the meaning expressed in Aristotle's words, "Man is a political animal".

The biological essence of a person includes his upright walking, the size of his body, the shape of his head, legs and arms, the ability to think, and a number of

other biological indicators that distinguish him from other creatures as a biological species.

The biological essence of a person can be attributed to his ability to walk upright. Therefore, the more upright a person is, the more handsome he looks.

Mother nature has created all its elements in a balanced way. Man is an element of nature.

While nature has created a balanced relationship between its elements, man has disturbed this balance as a result of his activities. It is natural that people living in a place where the balance of nature is disturbed will also suffer, because man is also a part of nature.

Conclusion.

It can be seen that these two views complement each other within the framework of philosophical analysis of man. Therefore, a person should be considered as a biosocial being. This shows that biologicalness in man is socially determined and that sociality has biological foundations.

To sum up, this unity, created by relating the biological stage of human development to the stage of social and cultural development, determines its essence.

The above comments indicate that a person is a complex, whole biosocial creature.

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